

**Synthesis of 6,7-Methylenedioxyisocoumarin
and Naphtho[1,2-*c*]isocoumarin**

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WE have earlier reported^{1,2} synthesis of alkaloid doryanine(10) from 4,5-methylenedioxyhomophthalic acid (1) via the dione (2). We now report synthesis of 8-acetyl-7-methyl-4,5-methylenedioxy-10,11-methylenedioxy-naphtho[1,2-*c*]isocoumarin (3) as the major product together with 4-carboxy-3-methyl-6,7-methylenedioxyisocoumarin (4) by treating 6,7-methylenedioxyhomophthalic acid (1) with acetic anhydride and pyridine (Scheme 1). Compounds 3 and 4 were also obtained by heating the dione (2) with pyridine (Tirodkar-Usgaonkar isocoumarin synthesis)³. The formation of such a naphthoisocoumarin was observed by Usgaonkar⁴ in the case of 4-methoxyhomophthalic acid but in negligible yield. The present reaction provides a good and simple synthesis for a type of compound 3 similar to the natural product like alternanol.

NOTES

Scheme 1

The structure of **3** has been confirmed by (i) elemental analysis and spectral data: $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1760 (C=O of COCH₃), 1710 (C=O of lactone) and 1640 (C=C); m/z M^+ 390. Compound **4** decarboxylates by heating above its melting point to give the isocoumarin (**5**) which has also been obtained by rearrangement of the dione (**2**) with concentrated H₂SO₄. Compounds **2**, **4** and **5** on heating with NaOH give the ketone (**11**) due to hydrolytic cleavage of the lactone or anhydride ring, as the case may be, followed by decarboxylation. The ketone (**11**) cyclodehydrates on heating above its melting point to give the isocoumarin (**5**). The ketone (**11**) cyclodehydrates when treated with sodium borohydride in methanol to form the dihydroisocoumarin (**12**).

Selenium dioxide oxidation of the isocoumarin (**5**) gives in good yield 3-formylisocoumarin (**6**) which on further oxidation with hydrogen peroxide in acetic acid forms 3-carboxyisocoumarin (**7**). Compound **7** decarboxylates to give the isocoumarin (**8**) which on treatment with methylamine gives alkaloid doryanine¹ (**10**).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard, ir

spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 237 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

Preparations of 3 and 4: A mixture of the acid (**1**; 0.005 mol), acetic anhydride (2 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 2 h. When a light brown solid separated. The mixture was poured on crushed ice with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The sticky mass obtained was triturated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave **4** which was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethyl acetate (0.1 g), m.p. 270–71° (Found: C, 57.7; H, 3.5. C₁₂H₈O₆ calcd. for: C, 58.00; H, 3.2%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3100–2800 (jagged bands OH of COOH), 1740 (C=O of lactone), 1700 (C=O of COOH) and 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

The insoluble residue found to be **3** was crystallised from dimethyl formamide, (0.5 g), m.p. 350–51° (Found: C, 67.5; H, 3.6. C₂₂H₁₄O₇ calcd. for: C, 67.7; H, 3.7%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1760 (C=O of COCH₃), 1710 (C=O of lactone), 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=C). m/z M^+ 198, 375, 361, 348, 319, 293, 289, 261, 233, 205, 187, 176, 175, 174 and 43.

Preparation of 5: The dione (**2**; 1 g) was heated with H₂SO₄ (5 ml; 80%) at 100° for 45 min and then poured on crushed ice. The resulting solid was triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution and filtered and the residue crystallised from benzene, m.p. 184–85° (Found: C, 64.8; H, 4.1. C₁₁H₈O₄ calcd. for: C, 64.7; H, 4.0%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1730 (C=O of lactone), 1660 (C=C) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic).

Compound **4** (0.2 g) on decarboxylation by heating above its melting point (~270°) in a metal-bath yielded **5**. The ketone (**11**) by mixing (0.5 g) with H₂SO₄ (5 ml, 90%) and keeping overnight at room temperature and pouring on crushed ice also yielded **5**.

Preparation of 11: Compounds **2**, **4** and **5** (0.5 g) were refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (10 ml; 10%) for 2 h, then cooled and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) (0.3 g), m.p. 164–65° (Found: C, 59.8; H, 4.2. C₁₁H₁₀O₅ calcd. for: C, 59.46; H, 4.5%).

Preparation of 12: Sodium borohydride (0.5 g) was added slowly to methanolic solution of **11** (0.5 g) in methanol (25 ml) with stirring at room temperature for 3 h. On acidification it gave a turbid solution which was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water, and then evaporated to yield a solid which was crystallised from benzene, (0.3 g), m.p. 155–56° (Found: C, 64.7; H, 4.8. C₁₁H₉O₄ calcd. for: C, 64.4; H, 4.4%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1710 (C=O of lactone) and 1620 cm⁻¹ (aromatic).

Preparation of 6: The isocoumarin (**5**) in dioxane (50 ml) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (10 g)

for 14 h and filtered hot. Dioxane was then removed by distillation and the resulting yellow solid was crystallised from dioxane. m.p. 280–81° (Found : C, 60.5 ; H, 2.7. $C_{11}H_8O_5$ calcd. for : C, 60.5 ; H, 2.7%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1 730 (C=O of lactone), 1 695 (C=O of aldehyde) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (aromatic) ; the 2,4-DNP of 6 m.p. 310°.

Preparation of 7 : Compound 6 (0.2 g) was added in small lots to a mixture of acetic acid (1 ml) and hydrogen peroxide (6 ml ; 30%). The resulting carboxyisocoumarin (7) separated after 20 h was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 340–41° (Found : C, 56.5 ; H, 2.6. $C_{11}H_8O_6$ calcd. for : C, 56.4 ; H, 2.5%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2 800–3 000 (jagged OH of COOH), 1 705br (C=O of lactone and C=O of COOH overlapped), 1 640 (C=C), 1 610 cm^{-1} (aromatic) ; the methyl ester of 7, m.p. 168–69°.

Preparation of 8 : The carboxycompound (7 ; 0.2 g) was decarboxylated using copper-bronze (0.1 g) in a metal-bath at $\sim 350^\circ$ for 45 min and the solution was then extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water, dried (sodium sulphate) and removal of ethyl acetate gave a pale yellow solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 168–69° (lit.¹ 168–69°) (Found : C, 63.0 ; H, 3.2. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ calcd. for : C, 63.15 ; H, 3.0%).

Preparation of 9 : A mixture of 6 (1 g), acetic anhydride (3 ml) and sodium acetate (1 g) was heated in an oil-bath at 170–80° for 6 h. The mixture was then poured on ice and the resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from acetic acid, (0.6 g), m.p. 320–21° (Found : C, 59.9 ; H, 3.0. $C_{13}H_8O_6$ calcd. for : C, 60.0 ; H, 3.0%) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2 500–3 000 (jagged OH of COOH), 1 730 (C=O of lactone), 1 680 (C=O of COOH) and 1 600 cm^{-1} (aromatic) ; its configuration as *trans* followed by nmr spectrum of its ethyl ester, m.p. 230–31° ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.36 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 4.32 (2H, q, CH_2CH_3), 6.2 (2H, s, O– CH_2 –O), 6.63 (1H, d, $CH=CH-COOC_2H_5$), 6.82 (1H, s, H-4), 6.97 (1H, s, H-5), 7.37 (1H, d, $CH=CHCOOC_2H_5$) and 7.68 (1H, s, H-8).

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